

MELTING BEHAVIOUR OF CF/PEEK COMPOSITE

Tien-Wei Shyr, Shuenn-Tong Yang, and Jiunn-Rong Kuo

Department of Textile Engineering,
Feng-Chia University,
Taichung, Taiwan, R.O.C.

ABSTRACT

The melting behaviour of CF/PEEK composite was investigated using both differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and hot stage polarized microscopy (HSPM). Double melting peaks were found by DSC. From the observation of melting behaviour of crystal by HSPM, the high temperature melting behaviour is mainly due to the melt of the crystal formed during isothermal crystallization; the low temperature melting behaviour is mainly due to the melt of the crystal formed during the cooling after isothermal crystallization. Transcrystalline structure was observed by HSPM as well. An analysis of fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) suggested that there is no chemical bonding between carbon fibre and PEEK. The studies of a wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) found that there is no different crystal reflection of CF/PEEK composite with and without transcrystalline structure.

Keywords: CF/PEEK composite, transcrystalline structure, double melting peaks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) is a semicrystalline thermoplastic material that is attracting current interest because of its high temperature stability and high mechanical properties. These include high melting point and glass transition temperature, combined with a wide range of attainable crystallinity, low flammability, and ease of processibility. It has become particularly attractive for advanced composite applications.

Recent studies of CF/PEEK have included investigation of its crystallization¹⁻⁶, and its properties^{7,8}. PEEK can be a completely amorphous material after quenching. It also becomes crystalline material under suitable conditions. However, melting behaviour could be varied under different crystallization conditions. Some literatures⁹⁻¹³ contain conflicting explanations of the double melting peaks. Two opposing models have been proposed. In the first of these^{9,10}, it is supposed that the crystals with the low melting

temperature form first and then transfer into a higher melting form during annealing or heating. The second model¹¹⁻¹³ suggested that the two melting peaks come from separate populations of crystals. The higher melting peak coming from the primary crystals and the lower melting peak coming from secondary crystals which may grow between the original crystals. In an attempt to clarify this phenomenon, the specimens of CF/PEEK model composites with and without a transcrystalline structure were used here. A combination of techniques such as fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) were employed to provide insights into the interphase between carbon fibre and PEEK.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

PEEK was used as supplied by ICI Ltd.. The material used here in this work is a development grade with melt viscosity of approximately 200 Pa s at 410 °C. APC-2 is a aromatic polymer prepreg supplied by ICI Ltd.. This material contains ca. 61% Hercules AS-4 carbon fibres (by volume) impregnated with ca. 39% PEEK.

2.2 Specimens preparation

2.2.1. Amorphous CF/PEEK model composite

Carbon fibres were placed between two thin films of PEEK as a wandwich. Here, carbon fibres have from APC-2 prepreg dissolved in α -chloronaphthalene at a temperature above ca.230 °C¹⁴. Amorphous CF/PEEK model composites were obtained by a hot stage polarized microscope (HSPM). The sample was first heated to 400 °C, at the rate of 20 °C/min, for 20 min, then quenched in liquid nitrogen.

2.2.2 CF/PEEK model composite with transcrystalline structure

The specimens were prepared using the recommened procedure for CF/PEEK model composite in a HSPM¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The sample was heated to 400 °C (at 20 °C/min) for 20min and then cooled at the rate of 40 °C/min to 305 °C, where it was held for 25min and then cooled to room temperature at 20 °C/min. Previous studies¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have shown that a transcrystalline layer was formed around the carbon fibre in this isothermal crystallization.

2.2.3 CF/PEEK model composite without transcrystalline structure

The specimens were obtained under non-isothermal crystallization. The sample was cooled at the rate of 20 °C/min after melting at 400 °C for 20min. CF/PEEK model composites were made without transcrystalline structure¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

2.3 Characterization techniques

To investigate the decomposition temperature of the materials, a TG/DTA Seiko 200 was used here. A sample mass is of 8 to 10 mg. The heating rate is 20

°C /min. A Perkin Elmer DSC-2 differential scanning calorimeter (calibrated using In and Pb) was utilized for the study of the melting and crystallization behaviour. To observe the transcrystallization and melting behaviour of CF/PEEK composite, a Leitz Laborlux 12 Pol S polarized microscope with Linkam THMS 600 hot stage (calibrated using In and Pb) was used here.

The interphase between carbon fibre and PEEK was studied using a combination of techniques such as FTIR and WAXS. A FTIR (Nicolet 520) with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ was used to investigate the band of the specimens. Here, the specimens were covered between two thin films of KBr salt plates. A Siemens D-500 diffractometer with nickel filtered CuK α radiation was used to obtain wide angle X-ray scattering patterns in reflection mode.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermogravimetric analysis

Before investigating the melting behaviour of CF/PEEK composite, it was necessary to establish, as a baseline, the thermal behaviour of this polymer in the absence of any added fibres. The weight loss of PEEK heated in nitrogen was first studied using thermogravimetry. The thermogravimetric curves showed that there was no weight loss of PEEK before 500 °C, and no weight loss of PEEK took place when the sample was held at 400 °C for 90min. 5% weight loss of the sample occurred at ca. 569 °C.

The thermogravimetric analysis of APC-2 is similar to that of PEEK. There was no weight loss, after the sample was held at 400 °C for 90min.

3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry

Thermal history of PEEK was investigated by DSC. At the heating rate of 20 °C/min, the peak temperature of the melting endotherm was about 339 °C, and the peak temperature of the crystallization exotherm was about 289 °C (at 20 °C/min), when the sample was held at 400 °C for 20min.

A limited investigation of isothermal crystallization of PEEK has been conducted. The sample was heated to 400 °C for 20min, then cooled at 40 °C/min to 305 °C (above the onset temperature of the exotherm ca. 295 °C). Held at 305 °C for 25min (after the leading edge intercepted the baseline), the sample was cooled to room temperature at 20 °C/min. A double peaks of the melting endotherm could be observed, when the sample reheated at 20 °C/min. The two melting peaks were at 317 °C and 342 °C, respectively.

The melting behaviour of APC-2 is different with PEEK. At the heating rate of 20 °C/min, the peak temperature of the melting endotherm is about 345 °C. Here, there is a 6 °C difference between neat PEEK and APC-2. It could be due to different grades between neat PEEK and APC-2 composite PEEK. Crystallization behaviour was studied by DSC after remelting at 400 °C for 20min. The peak temperature of the crystallization exotherm was about 286 °C. A double peaks of the melting endotherm could also be observed, when APC-2 was treated during an isothermal crystallization program with the same condition

of neat PEEK treated. The two melting peaks were 316 °C and 343 °C , respectively. There was no significant difference between the double melting peaks of neat PEEK and APC-2 composite.

The phenomenon of the multiple melting points was widely discussed in some literatures⁹⁻¹³, it appears that the phenomenon is not yet fully understood. It is necessary to further study the melting and crystallization behaviour using HSPM technique.

3.3 Polarized-light microscopy

For the observation of the morphology, a sample was prepared by a single carbon fibre placed between two thin films of PEEK. A CF/PEEK model composite with transcrystalline structure was obtained under isothermal crystallization. Optical micrograph of the transcrystalline interphase in the CF/PEEK system is illustrated in Figure 1. A well developed transcrystalline layer around carbon fibre and some large isolated spherulites, away from the fibre can be observed.

Figure 1. Photograph of a transcrystalline layer on Hercules AS-4 carbon fibre. PEEK isothermal crystallized at 305 °C for 25min. (crossed polars)

In Figure 2, a series of photographs was obtained during the isothermal crystallization. It indicated that a well developed transcrystalline layer and some large isolated spherulites were formed in the period of isothermal crystallization (at 305 °C) (see Figure 2a). A large number of small spherulites were formed after isothermal crystallization (see Figure 2c). A series of photographs, obtained from the reheated specimen, is shown in Figure 3. The colour of the specimen was changed at about 300 °C (see Figures 3a and 2d), it could be due to the beginning of the polymer melting. The colour of the specimen was changed obvious at 318 °C (see Figure 3b and 2c), which is the approximate

(a) at 305 °C for 25min

(b) cooled to 265 °C

(c) cooled to 256 °C

(d) cooled to 25 °C

Figure 2. The growth of transcrystalline layer and spherulites in a CF/PEEK model composite. Remelting temperature and time, cooling rate, and crystallization temperature are 400 °C , 20min, 40 °C , and 305 °C . Scale bar = 50 μ m. All prints are at the same magnification. (cross polars)

lower melting point. At 328 °C, small spherulites disappeared slowly, which had formed during the cooling time (see Figures 3c and 2b). However, large spherulites and transcrystalline layer were still there at 336 °C (see Figures 3d and 2a). The spherulites and transcrystalline layer disappeared at 342 °C. Figures 2 and 3 show that carbon fibre and heterogeneity are good nucleants for PEEK. Crystal first formed due to the carbon fibre and heterogeneities in the period of isothermal crystallization. Therefore, the lamellae of the transcrystalline layer and large spherulites are thicker than that of small spherulites formed during the cooling time. Two series of photographs (Figures 2 and 3) indicate that the high temperature melting behaviour was mainly due to the melt of the crystal formed in the period of isothermal crystallization and the low temperature melting behaviour was mainly due to the melt of the crystal formed at the cooling time after isothermal crystallization. The results are in a agreement with the second model¹¹⁻¹³. The appearance of multiple melting endotherms could have been due to the thickness difference of the lamellae¹⁸.

(a) at 300 °C

(b) at 318 °C

(c) at 328 °C

(d) at 336 °C

Figure 3. The melting of the CF/PEEK model composite with transcrystalline structure. Heating at 20 °C/min. Scale bar = 50 μ m. All prints are at the same magnification. (crossed polars)

3.4 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

A Typical spectra of a neat PEEK and CF/PEEK model composites with and without transcrystalline structure are shown in Figure 4. Distinctive spectral features of the neat PEEK specimen (see Figure 4c) included the carbonyl stretching vibration at 1652.4 cm^{-1} and two overlapping broad bands at 865.37 cm^{-1} and 839.56 cm^{-1} ; the skeletal in-plane vibration of the phenyl rings at 1599.8 cm^{-1} and 1491.9 cm^{-1} . Bands are associated with the carbonyl linkages at 1308.8 cm^{-1} and 1279.7 cm^{-1} ; the asymmetric stretching of the diphenyl ether groups at 1228.1 cm^{-1} and 1190.0 cm^{-1} ; the in-plane vibrations of the aromatic hydrogens at 1161.3 cm^{-1} ; and the aromatic C-H out-of-plane bending region at 1000 ~ 750 cm^{-1} . The results are similar to the value reported¹⁹. In comparison with the spectra of three different structural specimens(see Figure 4), there are no significant differences among of them. It may be further concluded that there is no bonding formed between PEEK and carbon fibre with or without transcrystalline structure.

Figure 4. Spectra of neat PEEK and CF/PEEK model composites. (a) CF/PEEK model composite with transcrystalline structure, (b) amorphous CF/PEEK model composite (a and b see 2.2.2. for description of the heat treatment), (c) neat PEEK with spherulites (obtained by melting at 400 °C for 25min then cooled to room temperature at 40 °C/min).

3.5 Wide angle X-ray Scattering

WAXS curves of CF/PEEK composites, made from APC-2 prepreg. with and without transcrystalline structure and amorphous structure are shown in Figure 5. The scattering intensity of amorphous CF/PEEK composite (see Figure 5a) consists of two crystalline reflections. The carbon fibre peak at 26° and the amorphous composite PEEK peak at 19° can be seen clearly. The curve is otherwise featureless. In Figure 5b, the curve of the CF/PEEK composite without transcrystalline structure indicates that the scattering consists of five crystalline reflections. In comparison with the previous report^{5,20}, the peaks (~ 18.7°, ~ 20.7°, ~ 22.6°, and ~ 28.7°) index as 110, 113, 200, and 213 for PEEK and the peak at ~ 26° index 002 for carbon fibre. The curve of the CF/PEEK composite with transcrystalline structure, shown in Figure 5c, consists of five crystalline reflections as well. There were no new crystalline reflections between CF/PEEK composite neither with nor without transcrystalline

Figure 5. WAXS intensity vs. scattering angle for CF/PEEK composites, (a) amorphous CF/PEEK composite, (b) CF/PEEK composite without transcrystalline, (c) CF/PEEK composite with transcrystalline structure (see 2.2.2. for description of the heat treatment).

structure. The scattering intensity of the composite with the transcrystalline structure is stronger at $\sim 18.7^\circ$ than that of composite without transcrystalline structure. This could be due to the effect of isothermal crystallization, but not the effect of the transcrystalline structure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A comparison of Figure 2 with Figure 3 demonstrates that the double melting endotherms come from the melting of two distinct crystal populations. These populations can be formed at the different crystallized conditions. In this study, the high temperature melting behaviour is mainly due to the melting of the crystal formed during isothermal crystallization and the low temperature melting behaviour is mainly due to the melting of the crystal formed during the cooling after isothermal crystallization.

In the study of the interface between carbon fibre and PEEK both with and without the transcrystalline structure, no obvious chemical bonding or functional group could be seen. The nucleation of transcrystalline growth appears to be a physical process. However, the reason for the development of the transcrystalline structure is not yet fully understood. This aspect still needs further investigation.

Figure 5 indicated that the crystal reflections of CF/PEEK composite with and without transcrystalline structure are similar. There is no different crystal reflection. It may further concluded that the transcrystalline structure and the spherulitic structure are the same in nature.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank the National Science Council of the Republic of China for the financial support of this work (NO. NSC 80-0210-D035-03).

References

1. J.N. Leckenby, D.C. Harget, W.J. Sichina, and P.S. Gill, in "Carbon Fibers, Technology, Uses, and Prospects", The Plastics and Rubber Institute London, pp86-89.
2. J.G. shukla and W.J. Sichina, SPE ANTEC 1984 Tech. Papers, 30, 265 (1984)
3. Y. Lee and R.S. Porter, Polym. Eng. Sci., 26, 633 (1986).
4. G.M.K. Ostberg and J.C. Seferis, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 33, 29 (1987).
5. P. Cebe, L. Lowry, S.Y. Chung, A. Yavrouian, and A. Gupta, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 34, 2273(1987).
6. D.J. Blundell, R.A. Crick, B. Fife, J. Peacock, A. Keller, and A. Waddon, J. Mater. Sci., 24, 2057(1989).
7. C.M. Tung and P.J. Dynes, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 33, 505(1987).
8. M.F. Talbott, G.S. Springer, and L.A. Berglund, J. Comp. Mater., 21, 1056(1987).
9. D.J. Blundell and B.N. Osbourn, Polym., 24, 953(1983).
10. D.J. Blundell, Polym., 28, 2248(1987).
11. P. Cebe and S.D. Hong, Polym., 27, 1183(1986).
12. D.C. Bassett, R.H. Olley, and I.A.M. Al Raheil. Polym., 29, 1745(1988).
13. S.Z.D. Cheng, M.Y. Cao, and B. Wunderlich, Macromolecules, 19, 1868(1986).
14. A.J. Lovinger and D.D. Davis, Polym. comm., 26, 322(1985).
15. T.W. Shyr, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Leed, U.K., (1989).
16. S.T. Yang, Master Thesis, Feng-Chia University, R.O.C., (1992).
17. J.R. Kuo, Master Thesis, Feng-Chia University, R.O.C., (1992).

18. M.P. Lattimer, J.K. Hobbs, M.J. Hill, and P.J. Barham, Polym., 33, 3971(1992)
19. H.X. Nguyen and H. Ishida, polym., 27, 1400(1986).
20. N.T. Wakelyn, Polym (Commun.), 25, 306(1984).